

Green Human Resource Management Practices in Bangladesh: Impediments and Remedies

Qazi Moinuddin Mahmud^{1*}

¹Department of Management, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

Abstract: Though sufficiently addressed in the extant literature, empirical evidence on the factors impeding GHRM implementation particularly in the context of multiple industries of Bangladesh is still lacking. Hence, this study aims to explore the critical barriers that an organization encounters in the path of GHRM execution, as well as to suggest some remedies in this respect. An in-depth semi-structured interview method is used in this qualitative research to collect rich and thick primary data from twenty-two participants who are selected using a convenience sampling technique. The six steps of thematic analysis as suggested by Braun and Clarke are followed to analyze the transcribed interview data. Findings indicate that unawareness, rebelliousness, paper-based culture, financial restraints, time constraints, demotivation, and incongruent regulatory policies are the major impediments to GHRM practices. It is also evident that these obstructions can be resolved by fostering learning, instituting reward systems, confirming employee participation, supporting a paper-less culture, leveraging technology, and aligning GHRM with the whole supply chain. Future researchers can use the exploratory findings of this study in their work. Moreover, HR practitioners and policymakers can also benefit from the suggestions made in this study.

Keywords: Green Human Resource Management, Sustainability, Impediments, Remedies, Bangladesh

*Corresponding Author: Qazi Moinuddin Mahmud

Accepted: 23 February, 2024; **Published:** 09 March, 2024

How to cite this article: Mahmud, Q. M. (2024). *Green Human Resource Management Practices in Bangladesh: Impediments and Remedies*. *North American Academic Research*, 7(2), 55-73. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10800580>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2024 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Green human resource management (GHRM) principally focuses on aligning human resource management (HRM) practices with the environmental goals of the organization in a planned and systematic manner (Jabbour 2013). It has been progressively becoming a critical approach for many organizations to engage with their workforce that is more environmentally aware. Realizing the significance of greening HRM practices, researchers across the world have commenced to ponder the GHRM applications in different organizations as a newfangled trend of research specifically in the field of environmental management (EM), intended at shaping HRM practices (Jabbour et al. 2015). Creating a sustainable workforce, which is the central agenda of GHRM is however, not that well-conceived in developing countries like Bangladesh (Islam et al. 2019). Despite the mounting concerns of environmental degradation, GHRM practices at workplace remains a poorly explored phenomenon in the context of Bangladesh. Though limited in number, prior empirical studies conducted in Bangladesh perspective mostly covered the awareness and implication aspects of GHRM (Chowdhury et al. 2019; Mamun 2019; Rakin et al. 2020; Saha et al. 2020; Ullah et al. 2020; Islam et al. 2021; Rubel

et al. 2021; Rubel et al. 2021; Kamrunnahar et al. 2023; Noor et al. 2023; Rupa et al. 2023). The impediments and complications involved in applying GHRM practices are not rigorously studied and identified. Only one empirical research was so far conducted in the context of Bangladesh RMG industry, exploring the challenges and solutions concerning GHRM practices (Islam et al. 2019). However, that study used a relatively small sample size and encompassed only the ready-made garment factories, and hence restricting the extent of generalizability. A significant research gap thus exists in the extant literature on the impediments of adopting GHRM practices, specifically in the context of Bangladesh. The present study tries to bridge this knowledge gap through inductive exploration. The two specific research questions addressed in this study are as follows:

1. What impediments does an organization confront while implementing GHRM practices?
2. What actions does an organization need to undertake to overcome the impediments involved in GHRM implementation?

Through recognizing the major obstacles and constraints with regard to GHRM practices as well as recommending the potential solutions based on in-depth interview data, this exploratory research intends to contribute to the knowledge. The empirical findings of this study will provide HR practitioners and policymakers with invaluable insights to tap the opportunity in GHRM adoption. Moreover, this exploration would benefit international organizations, campaigners, and many other stakeholders in promoting the implementation of GHRM practices particularly in a developing country like Bangladesh, where this concept is not well conceived yet.

2. Literature review:

The concept of GHRM is relatively new which has emerged from the discourse of sustainable development and corporate sustainability. In the year 1996, this concept was coined by Wehrmeyer who argued that employees are the ultimate keys for their companies to successfully adopt an environmentally concerned approach to organizational activities (Tomer and Rana 2020). It is basically a multidisciplinary concept encompassing various theories and methods from diverse disciplines including management (Ren et al. 2018). However, a universally accepted definition of GHRM is yet to be found, since numerous scholars and practitioners conceptualized it in varied ways and from different perspectives. GHRM can be viewed as the integration of environmental management into HRM. Renwick et al. (2013) described GHRM as the HRM-related aspects of environmental management that accentuates the role of HRM in preventing pollution through the operational processes of an organization.

GHRM is largely used to imply the contribution of HRM policies and practices to the broader environmental agenda of the organization (Vij et al. 2013). The relevance of GHRM lies in the fact that employees' personal lives are greatly impacted by the environmental issues in various ways (Benevene and Buonomo 2020). The reason is not merely that a quality environment has obvious impacts on the quality of employees' lives, but rather because employees' behavior, values, and choices are directly connected with environmental questions (Taylor and Lawrence 2012). Therefore, throughout the acquisition, development, and maintenance functions of the HRM process, GHRM is concerned with forming a green workforce that will understand, appreciate, and practice green initiatives to meet green objectives of the organization (Mathapati 2013). All the functions and efforts relating to GHRM essentially focus on encouraging environment-friendly behavior among that green workforce to support achieving an organization's sustainability goals.

Management scholars and researchers around the world have already identified and analyzed various HRM related functions that can enable an organization to secure the positive impacts of GHRM, leading to the environmental

competitiveness in turn (Mamun 2019). Reviewing and integrating the findings of previous studies, Mamun (2019) presented a list of GHRM practices that are relevant to each traditional HRM function including job design and analysis, human resource planning, recruitment, selection, orientation, performance management, training and development, reward management, health and safety management, discipline management, and employee relations. Based on the findings of the prior studies, Pham et al. (2020) listed the definitions of these GHRM functions, and also added some other GHRM related functions such as employee involvement and empowerment, organizational culture, role of unions in environmental management, organizational learning, work-life balance, green health and safety. In fact, GHRM includes all the HRM functions that integrate environmental management practices. For example, green hiring, which is a pivotal component of GHRM practices involves highlighting the environmental aspects in recruitment and selection process (Longoni et al. 2018). Three aspects such as green awareness, green employer branding, and green criteria are encompassed in green hiring process (Saeed et al. 2019). The second major GHRM function is green training and development which requires implementing policies to increase employees' environmental awareness and skills, and to improve their green abilities and expertise (Renwick et al. 2013). Green training and development imply a combined approach, stimulating employees to acquire and apply environmental safety skills as well as to be more cognizant about environmental aspects that are crucial in achieving environmental goals (Jabbour 2011). The third major GHRM function is green performance management and appraisal which requires establishing a system to evaluate employees' performance in the process of environmental management (Jabbour and Santos 2008). Policies need to be in place in this respect to monitor and evaluate the performance of employees in terms of accomplishing environmental objectives (Govindarajulu and Daily 2004). Green reward and compensation are another vital GHRM function, which according to Jabbour et al. (2010), systematically incorporates both financial and nonfinancial rewards for those employees who contribute towards achieving the environmental goals of the organization.

All these GHRM related functions, as it is manifested in the extant literature, have had substantial positive impacts in fostering organizational sustainability (Ehnert 2009; Prasad 2013; Renwick et al. 2013; Mahmood et al. 2016). Through employee engagement, GHRM elevates environmentally friendly activities at the workplace (Kapil 2015). It is evident that GHRM practices can enable an organization to save costs, find new business opportunities, and prevent conservational problems (Mehta and Chugan, 2015). The findings of the previous studies clearly reflect that systematic GHRM practices result in reduced cost, improved efficiency, effective employee engagement, and increased talent retention that subsequently facilitate organizations to lessen carbon emissions (Mehta and Chugan 2015; Dumont et al. 2016). The positive impacts of adopting GHRM practices that Bangladeshi organizations particularly experience are also evident in the existent literature (Chowdhury et al. 2019; Rakin et al. 2020; Saha et al. 2020; Islam et al. 2021; Rubel et al. 2021; Rubel et al. 2021; Rupa et al. 2023). For instance, surveying several HR professionals who work either in manufacturing or service firms in Bangladesh, Rupa et al. (2023) found that effective GHRM practices positively influence the environmental performance of an organization. In case study research conducted in the context of a large Bangladeshi commercial bank, Chowdhury et al. (2019) revealed that the impacts of GHRM practices on employee job satisfaction is significantly positive. In a correlational research, Islam et al. (2021) discovered that a significantly positive relationship exists between GHRM practices and employee retention. However, the findings of all these empirical studies are consistent given that job performance, job satisfaction, and employee retention are strongly connected with each other that can be substantially impacted by an organization's GHRM practices.

However, though literature on the difficulties and impediments relating to GHRM implementation is limited, some challenges in this regard can be identified from the findings of previous studies. Prior empirical findings imply that the financial significance of an organization's GHRM practices is not beyond doubt since the technology adoption cost required for ensuring green practices is huge (Bohdanowicz 2006). It is also evident that poor financial return of GHRM

practices might negatively affect other organizational functions (Guerci and Carollo 2016). The knowledge gap of the managers is also found to be a major problem in applying GHRM practices in the workplace (Smedley 2007). Educational institutions can be made responsible in this respect since GHRM related courses are not widely offered there to prepare potential knowledgeable green employees for the organizations (Brockett 2007). Prior studies entail that lack of managerial support as well as the increased cost of GHRM practices are some of the common difficulties that many organizations might encounter while endeavoring to implement GHRM in the organization (Jafri 2012; Fayyazi et al. 2015; Ren et al. 2018).

However, the potential impediments relating to GHRM implementation that HR managers specifically working in Bangladeshi organizations combat are not well explored. Though empirical findings in this regard are very limited, a few studies merely listed some common barriers such as lack of awareness and support, high implementation cost, unskilled workforce, etc. (Saha et al. 2020). This list of barriers is, however, not identified following appropriate research methodology rather represents the authors' own perspectives (Saha et al. 2020). On the other hand, Anjum et al. (2022) in a qualitative study conducted on banking professionals found that most of the Bangladeshi banks have already adopted GHRM in their operations with the aid of electronic HRM. However, while practicing GHRM electronically, these banks face some critical hurdles including poor knowledge, heavy cost, technical difficulties, and lack of organizational support. (Anjum et al. 2022). Based on the participants' opinions, Anjum et al. (2022) also proposed some actions to overcome these problems such as developing awareness, boosting organizational support, enhancing technical expertise, constant monitoring, appropriate rewarding, etc. Nevertheless, the findings of this study (Anjum et al. 2022) cannot be generalized even in Bangladesh context since the participants were selected only from a single industry.

Hence, it is crucial to explore the major impediments and remedies of GHRM implementation in the context of multiple industries of Bangladesh for a more comprehensive understanding on this vital phenomenon. Considering different industries for such an exploration would help to draw a more generalizable conclusion.

3. Methodology:

This qualitative research was conducted in Bangladesh perspective to explore the obstacles and remedies of GHRM practices in different types of organization. A qualitative research design was employed in this study since research on the chosen topic particularly in the context of a developing country like Bangladesh is very limited, requiring an in-depth exploration to comprehend the obstructions involved in GHRM execution as well as to suggest potential remedies in this respect. Moreover, an in-depth qualitative interview method that this research applied was necessary to obtain participants' subjective feelings, views, and experiences regarding the complex nature of GHRM practices (Saunders et al. 2015). The use of a qualitative exploratory research design was thus justified to grasp the poorly investigated phenomenon that this inquiry deals with. However, a non-probability sampling method called 'convenience sampling' was applied to select participants for this study that allowed the researcher to select samples based on his ease of access (Mathews and Ross 2010). The participants were chosen based on their accessibility and readiness to participate. Details of the interviews are listed here wherein the name of the research participants or interviewees are kept anonymous.

Table: Interview details

Serial number	Interviewee's code	Academic qualification	Current position	Type of organization	Mode of interview	Length of interview
1	P1	MBA	Head of HRD	Beverage company	In-person	60 minutes
2	P2	MBA	FAVP	Financial trading company	In-person	30 minutes
3	P3	Postgraduate	HR Manager	Fintech company	In-person	75 minutes
4	P4	MBA (DU)	Principal officer, HRD	Bank PLC	In-person	40 minutes
5	P5	M.Com, PGDHRM	Vice president, HRD	Insurance company	In-person	120 minutes
6	P6	BBA	Chief Human Resource Officer (CHRO)	NBFI	In-person	30 minutes
7	P7	BBA, MBA (NSU)	Executive manager (Learning and Development)	Social enterprise chain	In-person	35 minutes
8	P8	MBA, MPMHRM (DU)	HR Manager	Asset management company	Telephone	25 minutes
9	P9	BBA, MBA	HR Manager	Private Bank	Google Meet	45 minutes
10	P10	BBA (EWU)	Country HR Manager	British multinational retailer	In-person	45 minutes
11	P11	MBM (BIBM)	HR Manager	Private Bank	In-person	60 minutes
12	P12	BBA, MBA (IUB)	HR Manager	Real estate company	In-person	21 minutes
13	P13	BBA (IBA, DU)	HR Analyst	Asset management company	Google Meet	32 minutes
14	P14	BBA, MBA (RU)	Chief Human Resource Officer (CHRO)	Bank PLC	In-person	60 minutes
15	P15	MBA	HR Manager	Outsourcing and technology	In-person	35 minutes

				services company		
16	P16	LLB, LLM, PGDHRM, MPHRM	Head of Employee Relations	Bank PLC	In-person	30 minutes
17	P17	BBA	HR Professional	Bank PLC	In-person	55 minutes
18	P18	BBA, MBA (NSU)	EVP & Head of HRD	Mobile financial service company	In-person	60 minutes
19	P19	BBA, MBA (EWU)	HR Manager	Expert advisory & consulting firm	In-person	42 minutes
20	P20	BBA, MBA (DU)	HR Manager	Bank PLC	In-person	45 minutes
21	P21	LLB, Bar-At-Law	Head of HR & Legal Division	Bank PLC	Both In-person & Online	80 minutes
22	P22	MBA	DGM	NBFI	In-person	40 minutes

However, prior to each interview, the research aims and objectives were succinctly explained to the participants so that they could give informed consent voluntarily. Moreover, the procedures concerning protecting confidentiality and anonymity were also clarified to uphold the ethical standards and to preserve the research integrity. A semi-structured interview guide consisting of seven thematic questions was followed during the interview to explore different themes such as, the barriers and complexities involved in the GHRM execution process as well as the potential actions that are required to overcome them. Twenty-two in-depth interviews lasting for on average an hour were carried out, which were recorded and later transcribed fully in English. The transcribed interview data were manually analyzed following the six steps of thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke 2006). It facilitated the researcher in analyzing a detailed account of the textual data in a step-by-step framework.

The researcher, at first, transcribed all the twenty-two interviews word by word and then organized the transcripts separately in file folders to ensure better data handling. The researcher read and re-read the transcribed textual data several times and noted down the initial memos and ideas to confirm data familiarization. The initial codes were subsequently generated from the data, representing a range of emergent themes. The researcher accomplished the coding process by underlining the relevant texts in the transcriptions and dragged them over to pertinent nodes. The nodes were then collated into eighteen broad categories. Two key themes of this exploration were determined by collating codes into potential themes and grouping the related data into befitting themes. Afterwards, the researcher reviewed, defined, and named the major themes that ultimately represent the key findings of this exploratory study.

However, the next section presents empirical evidence concerning two major thematic areas that were generated from analyzing the transcribed interview data.

4. Findings:

4.1 Theme: Impediments to GHRM implementation

4.1.1 Limited understanding and awareness:

Lack of understanding and awareness is a critical factor, adversely affecting the adoption of GHRM practices. Most of the interviewed participants (60%) argued that limited awareness, understanding, and knowledge is one of the major impediments in the path of GHRM implementation. Participant P6 who is the Chief Human Resource Officer of a reputed NBFIs stated that, with regard to GHRM practice, the most difficult task for the HR team is to engage the employees in the new transition process of moving from traditional HRM practice to comprehensive GHRM practice. P6 explained that their employees are mostly unaware of the benefits of GHRM practices that they might derive both at individual and organizational level. Since employees do not properly comprehend the GHRM concept, they perceive it as unreasonably challenging. Participant P12 who is an HR manager of a large real estate company also contended that despite taking GHRM initiatives at every HRM function, they find it difficult to execute GHRM due the poor knowledge and awareness of the huge number of employees involved in the workplace. The following excerpt demonstrates this phenomenon.

“Our employees lack awareness about the GHRM. They do not have a proper understanding about it. Being an HR manager, it’s a tough job for me to take care of them as we have a large group of people working here.” [P12]

Participant P20 who is an HR manager of a public bank similarly uttered that developing GHRM plans or financing the respective interventions is not a big problem for a financial organization like them but creating awareness among the whole workforce regarding these aspects is not that easy task to be accomplished. Interviewing HR professionals who work for different types of organizations in Bangladesh, a common barrier has actually been found in this exploration which is the employees’ lack of awareness and understanding of the significance of integrating environmental sustainability into HRM functions as well as the potential positive impacts of GHRM initiatives on the organizational overall sustainability efforts. This aspect is reflected in the following verbatim.

Potential resistance to adopting Green Human Resource Management at our organization arises from several factors. Firstly, a significant challenge we face is the need for a mindset shift among internal stakeholders, I mean our employees. Many failed to grasp the significance of integrating environmental sustainability into HR functions. Secondly, some people struggle to connect with the broader environmental goals, possibly due to a lack of awareness or understanding of the potential benefits and positive impact of GHRM on the organization’s overall sustainability efforts. [P17]

The findings of this empirical study clearly demonstrate that limited awareness and knowledge about the GHRM endeavors and impacts lead to perceived disruption of traditional HRM practice, noncooperation, resistance, and poor involvement of the employees [P2, P3, P6, P7, P10, P11, P15, P18, P19, P22], all of which subsequently hinder the implementation of GHRM practice in the workplace. However, inadequate training can be attributed as the underlying cause behind this obstruction since most of the participants agreed that addressing employees’ knowledge and skills gap is pivotal unless which misconceptions regarding GHRM interventions and impacts cannot be minimized. Participant P22 uttered that higher management does not always consider the necessity for retraining and hence employees fail to overcome their knowledge deficit on environmental sustainability. This phenomenon can be recognized from the following extract too.

"We don't think our management understands how important a sustainable workplace is. For instance, learning about environmentally responsible conduct is not covered in a separate training program." [P3]

It is evident in this study that neither the top management of the organizations operating in Bangladesh addresses the necessity to educate their mass employees about GHRM practices and principles, nor the employees themselves have the required literacy on sustainable practices, and hence GHRM implementation at the workplace is often hindered.

4.1.2 Resistance to change:

"It is also necessary to make the people understand the impact of depleting the use of resources. In implementing GHRM practices, the first and foremost block that I see is changing people's mindset, making them understand why we are doing these. Because of the lack of awareness and understanding regarding the GHRM practices, the employees and the managers are resistant to change" [P6]

Most of the participants viewed that resistance to change is an outcome of limited employee awareness and rigid managerial mindset which is reflected in the above extract. Participant P6 opined that GHRM practices are sometimes perceived to increase employees' total workload, leading employees to resist it. Besides, whenever the top-level HR executives or leaders themselves do not sufficiently demonstrate commitment to GHRM, general staff view this practice as a low-priority initiative and hence tend to resist it [P6]. The HR manager of a private commercial bank, P9 informed that the employees working in his organization are fully committed to the mission and vision of GHRM, but they do sometimes resist some GHRM initiatives particularly those that push them into discomfort zone. However, this reluctance and resistance to adapt GHRM practices is contemplated as a critical impediment for GHRM execution by twelve participants of this study.

"On the HR front, resistance from employees accustomed to traditional HR practices is another challenge. Transitioning to new, eco-friendly methods and tools requires change management, and not all employees may readily embrace these changes." [P9]

"Our employees do not accept the change too easily. Sometimes we are just too tired of asking them not to use extra lights in the office. Even though we have support staff to take care of the consumption of the energy, they cannot act on it properly because of the senior employees". [P12]

4.1.3 Deeply ingrained paper-based practice:

Analyzing the transcribed interview data, it is discovered that the traditional paper based HRM practices cause a critical barrier to the execution of the organizational GHRM policies. Some participants explicitly argued that becoming completely paperless in every HR related task is almost impossible for which GHRM practices are severely hindered [P4, P6, P8, P9, P12, P20]. According to participant P12, an ecofriendly HRM system enables to perform HR related functions with either less or no use of paperwork. P12, like many other participants stated that paper-based practice has been deeply rooted in their regular HRM functions, causing the HRM process to be slow and cumbersome and thereby hindering the agility required for effective GHRM practice. It can be however noted that compared to other types of organizations, financial companies rely more on paper-based work and hence face difficulties in executing paperless ecofriendly GHRM practices. From the following quotes it can be understood that overreliance on paper-based practices poses a major threat to GHRM implementation.

"From the perspective of Bangladesh, the banking industry still hasn't gone paperless. Where there is paper money, paper-based work is going on. Paper is a major threat to the environment.... Paperless banking or HR practice cannot be implemented properly at this moment. Because, even now, customers and employees still prefer paper or written documents, not anything in digital format.... If I say about employees, a complete digital archive or digital recording could not be implemented yet." [P4]

"Certainly, implementing GHRM practices comes with its own set of challenges, some of which we've already encountered. One of the significant hurdles is the deeply ingrained traditional practices in the banking industry, such as heavy reliance on paper-based

documentation. While we're working towards reducing paper usage, we must acknowledge that it's an industry-wide practice, and many stakeholders still prefer hard copies of documents. This presents a challenge in eliminating paper from our operations." [P9]

"One significant roadblock we're hitting is that some of our higher executives are pretty set in their ways and still prefer paper documents. There's comfort in that familiar way and moving away from that can cause a bit of friction. Changing long-standing practices and beliefs doesn't happen overnight." [P8]

The above last extract indicates that the rigid mindset of top-level executives regarding the long-standing paper-based practice is a primary obstacle in implementing GHRM practices. It is evident that establishing a paperless culture at the workplace with top-management's support remains a big challenge for Bangladeshi organizations which is however a precondition for GHRM implementation as well as long term organizational sustainability.

4.1.4 Financial constraint:

Financial limitations indeed pose a significant impediment to the implementation of GHRM practices. Most of the participants (60%) of this study overtly stated that one of the biggest obstacles they deal with while adopting GHRM is the cost factor or budget limitations. The financial issue is so limiting factor here that even the participant P10 who is the country HR manager of a British multinational retailer working in Bangladesh decisively uttered that his HR team encounters financial constraints in this regard. P10 informed that they always need to trade off their green initiatives due to monetary limitations. In his opinion, developing a workforce with the necessary green skills is a costly investment and its return cannot always be fully realized [P10]. Organizations essentially require developing a high-tech infrastructure along with IT specialists for GHRM execution, which involves huge investment. Majority of HR professionals interviewed for this study stated that the upper management of the company is found to be bit unwilling to make such a big investment for GHRM initiatives to become successful. The following quotes evidently represent this reality.

"Our business is going to incur more expenses in order to implement GHRM through electronic media. It costs a lot to develop software, maintain it continuously, train employees, and hire IT specialists." [P3]

"Another big struggle we do face is to convince our upper management to allocate proper resources to make these changes happen, as they require heavy investments in eco-friendly technologies, processes, and employee training. Going completely paperless is crucial for GHRM implementation which requires a lot of investments in areas like purchasing professional software and other eco-friendly technologies and processes. Convincing our upper bosses about these changes and making them understand the ROI is tough." [P7]

"Although the direct effect of going paperless is cost saving, its indirect effects are more significant. Specifically, if the demand for paper decreases altogether, less trees would be cut down. Alongside that, it is also a catalyst for an increase in electronic use, thus utilizing modern technology to its fullest potential. Using energy-star electronic items is also an eco-friendly way of contributing to sustainability. Nonetheless, it should also be noted that at the initial stage these actions can be quite costly. This is simply because paper is much cheaper than its electronic counterpart. However, in the long run costs will decrease as electronics are long-lasting and can easily be operational for 5 years or more, as opposed to the frequent purchasing of paper and printer/copier ink (paper and ink are complementary products). Heavy investment at initial phase is burdensome, however." [S21]

From the above verbatims it can be comprehended that insufficient financial resources negatively impact the adoption of green initiatives and strategies within the organization. Spending on technology adoption and employee training is of course vital for GHRM implementation, but it might have a big impact on a company's short-term financial results as well [P8]. Given that many organizations struggle financially and the short run benefit of GHRM interventions is not that apparent, budget limitation remains a critical issue for the HR team to execute GHRM functions effectively.

4.1.5 Time limitations:

Findings of this study imply that limited time can indeed pose a critical challenge for GHRM implementation. Regardless of their organization's type, every participant more or less agreed that balancing their HR practices with green initiatives takes a lengthy period. Participant P2 uttered that the time required to initiate GHRM procedures is a significant barrier to their widespread adoption. Concerning this matter, participant P4 explained the reason precisely that it takes long time for the HR team to convert the conventional HRM practices into sustainable HRM practices. Participant P17 argued that enhancing employee engagement in GHRM interventions and aligning the organizational values with broader environmental goals cannot be made happen overnight. Participant P8 opined that shifting to GHRM practices requires major changes in organizational culture, systems, and employee attitudes which is naturally a time-consuming process. The following extracts succinctly represent this reality that extended time requirement is an impediment in the path of effective GHRM implementation.

"Even though we've already started integrating Green HRM practices, the transition isn't instant—it's a marathon, not a sprint. It takes time to fully implement these changes across the board." [P8]

"Our organization is now implementing Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices, which requires adjustments to existing policies and systems, requiring collaboration and multifaceted functional alignment. This eventually requires a good amount of hard work and more importantly a huge amount of time and patience as well. This time involvement, I guess, is a big problem". [P17]

"Employee involvement is critical for GHRM implementation. We must properly describe the benefits of it to them to get their support. Employees' effectiveness in this case may be affected if they do not adopt these practices well. It's also about cultivating a sustainable culture. All these things take huge amount of time and work and that's a big challenge." [P19]

4.1.6 Demotivation:

"If there are no obvious incentives, rewards, or acknowledgment for their efforts, employees can be reluctant to fully engage with GHRM." [P3]

The above quote implies that motivating employees to vigorously engage in green initiatives is crucially needed. It is evident that the success in GHRM implementation largely relies on the mindset and commitment of employees to support eco-friendly practices. If employees do not notice any reward for their endeavors in GHRM execution, they tend not to contribute wholeheartedly. Ensuring employees' active participation in environmental and sustainability efforts is a hurdle if employees are neither intrinsically nor extrinsically motivated by the management [P10]. In this exploratory study, it is also found that compared to young employees, senior managers are more difficult to be encouraged with respect to GHRM execution which is perhaps due to the fact that they are less likely to appreciate changes [P3]. The HR managers might even feel that GHRM policy imposes additional responsibilities and workloads on their shoulders and hence become demotivated [P1]. However, most of the interviewed participants explicitly uttered that many employees of their organizations do not get the required impetus to adopt new green behaviors due to bounded organizational support. Employees instead continue following the conventional approach of performing things. The presence of recognition and rewards for GHRM endeavors is limited in almost every type of organization covered in this study and consequently poor employee motivation has been found to be one of the major impediments to GHRM implementation.

4.1.7 Incongruent regulatory policies:

Compatible regulatory policy is essentially needed for GHRM initiatives to be effectively accomplished. Unfortunately, financial companies in Bangladesh such as bank, NBF, asset management firm extensively craft and use paper-based physical documents as part of the regulatory requirements of Bangladesh Bank, Department of Financial Institutions

and Markets, and Securities and Exchange Commission which is certainly a counterproductive act from GHRM perspective [P4, P6, P8, P11, P13, P20]. Transcribed data suggest that in comparison to other types, financial organizations are more bound to comply with such incongruent regulatory policies which according to the research participants is one of the major impediments in achieving GHRM objectives. Participant P4 mentioned that their journey toward GHRM implementation is challenged by some key factors, one of which is the regulatory obligations for physical documentation. Participant P6 stated that unless the regulatory bodies of Bangladesh minimize their requirements, optimal utilization of resources will not be feasible. In fact, compliance with regulatory requirements increases complexity to the adoption of GHRM [P8]. The regulatory bodies' anticipations and stringent regulations are often in direct conflict with an organization's paperless or in other words sustainability goals [P8]. Moreover, it is apparent in this study that any form of misalignment between GHRM principles and regulatory requirements has the potential to limit an organization's capability to embrace sustainable practices in all respect [P8]. For example, a hard and fast regulatory policy regarding office hours can hamper sustainable HR practices [P6]. However, it can be easily comprehended from the following verbatims that differing rules and policies of regulators necessarily lead to confusion and hinder GHRM adoption.

"For example, Bangladesh Bank set a specific office time, from 9am to 5pm. Cutting down office time so that we can optimally use electricity. But if you are required to give certain deliverables in a timely way to run the business, you cannot just close the office and leave. Instead, it is seen that lights are switched off from outside, but all the processes are going on inside. When a policy is being formed, it must take into consideration which areas of their requirement are being impacted, so that it is properly addressed in the policy. Only then we can change our way of working". [P6]

"Yeah, that's a good point. Our external stakeholders, particularly the regulatory bodies like the Bangladesh Bank and the Securities and Exchange Commission, have certain requirements that we need to comply with. These often involve a lot of documentation and records that they currently expect in a certain format, sometimes hard copies, which can be at odds with our green initiatives like going paperless. So, there's this delicate balancing act we have to perform. We're committed to Green HRM, but we also have to navigate the compliance landscape carefully." [P8]

"Another challenge stems from external regulations and policies. In some instances, regulatory requirements mandate the use of physical documents or signatures, which can contradict our GHRM efforts. Striking a balance between compliance and sustainability is a delicate task." [P9]

So, from the above verbatims it is pretty clear that the policies set by the regulatory bodies in Bangladesh often conflict with the underlying assumptions of GHRM, and thus GHRM implementation becomes a difficult task for many organizations. In addition to the above discussed obstructions, participants identified some other issues that impede the adoption of GHRM at their workplace such as, measuring and reporting difficulties [P3, P10, P11], technological hurdles [P3, P8, P11], cultural disparities within workforce [P19], short-term investment focus [P7, P22], and alignment and coordination complexities [P10, P20, P22].

4.2 Theme: Actions required for overcoming impediments to GHRM implementation

4.2.1 Promoting employee learning:

All the participants of this study strongly suggested that learning is essentially required in order to overcome employees' misconceptions regarding GHRM interventions as well as their resistance to change, which are critical impediments to GHRM implementation. The interview data implies that **employee education and training** not only impart knowledge and skills but rather promote a positive attitude, and thereby aligning the total workforce with the green goals of the organization. Participants in the following ways emphasized the role of employee learning in overcoming the hurdles with regard to GHRM practices.

“To guarantee that staff members comprehend the significance of sustainability and their part in accomplishing company objectives, give them a thorough education and training” [P3]

“I can’t stress enough how important it is to keep everyone up to date. I mean, things change fast, and we want to make sure everyone’s on the same page, not just knowing what to do but really getting the hang of it. So, rolling out ongoing training? That’s key.” [P8]

“We can conduct more and more training and awareness programs to help employees transition smoothly into a digital and eco-friendly workplace. It’s about instilling the belief that these changes are not just about being environmentally responsible but also about simplifying their work processes and enhancing efficiency.” [P9]

“I will suggest raising more awareness by holding workshops and seminars so the employees can learn and practice green methods. Also, the HR department can give special consideration to jobseekers who already know about sustainable finance.” [P21]

4.2.2 Establishing reward system:

Poor employee motivation for GHRM practices has been identified as a crucial impediment in this study and participants in this regard stressed on the importance of establishing a robust reward system within the workplace to encourage employees comply with the GHRM policies unreservedly. The following extract represents the viewpoints of most of the participants that without rewarding green behavior, an organization cannot anticipate its employees to work hard for GHRM implementation.

“Rewards for workers who demonstrate green practices can be a potential motivator and I believe it can help encouraging people to work for GHRM execution.” [P2]

4.2.3 Ensuring employees’ active participation:

“Then, we need to involve employees at all levels in the process. Seek all your inputs, address your concerns, and make you guys active participants in GHRM initiatives.” [P10]

The above quote highlights the necessity of active participation of the entire workforce to make GHRM initiatives successful. Participants across different organizations stated in the same way that without employees’ active involvement and participation, GHRM policies will be almost impossible to execute. Participant P19 advocated that employee support is crucial for effective GHRM practice and to ensure that management has to clearly explain the interests that are mutually inclusive for employees and the employer.

4.2.4 Nurturing a paper-less culture:

In this study, it is found that a deeply ingrained paper-based practice inhibits effective GHRM practice in every type of organization. Participants, particularly those serving financial companies strongly suggested that having a completely digital platform in the workplace to reduce the unnecessary usage of paper is mandatory for overcoming this barrier. The following verbatim focuses on the significance of paper-less hiring practices for which a befitting culture needs to be built at first in the organization.

“Even now, we receive hard copies of CVs through the mail, and they are received physically at the Head Office. If we can do something like give out a hotline number or a shared email address where the applicants may share their queries and make the whole circular process digital. So, if there is a process such that if someone wants to apply for XXX Bank, then the applicants need to make a CV and submit it in the portal, and the notification will also be received by the applicant digitally. No letter will be sent, and the joining process has a record form that can be digitalized through a portal where the applicant will put all his information digitally. If we can do all these in the future, we can decrease the use of pen and paper. As per the policy, our work will be done by keeping a scanned copy of the new recruit’s documents, and we won’t need to print it unless it’s necessary. We essentially need to establish such a culture to practice GHRM effectively.” [P4]

4.2.5 Leveraging technology:

A huge financial investment in technology adoption is necessary for GHRM practices to be executed which poses a significant challenge for most of the organizations the participants of this study are employed with. Moreover, some participants opined that trust in technology is a nuanced complexity. Participant P8 stated that the shift towards a digital system might introduce a vulnerability that employees and management may be cautious about, especially with respect to data security, privacy, and potential system failure. Hence, P8 suggested that management should not only ensure the robustness of IT infrastructure but also manage employees' perception regarding its reliability. The problem is made more difficult by the fact that technology needs to be updated all the time, which involves financial outlay and moreover people may not like each new change every time. However, leveraging technology is the ultimate solution to this problem which according to most of the participants will eventually facilitate implementing GHRM policies and practices. The following extract indicates the importance of full-fledged technology adoption for sustainable HRM practices.

"This one's about not just having the tech but really using it to its full potential. Making sure it's doing the heavy lifting for us, making green choices the easy choices." [P8]

Most of the participants strongly agreed that successful adoption of GHRM can be made possible through practicing electronic HRM. The application of information technology can enable an organization to manage various HRM functions in a sustainable manner. Moreover, participants recommended some other actions for overcoming impediments to effective GHRM practices such as forming dedicated GHRM team [P18], thorough monitoring [P11, P12], integrating sustainability metrics into performance evaluation system [P7, P11], and securing leadership support [P2, P3, P7].

4.2.6 Aligning GHRM with the supply chain:

Data suggests that aligning GHRM policies and practices with the overall supply chain of the organization can help overcome barriers to GHRM implementation. Almost 60% interviewed participants stated that it is pivotal to establish a strategic relationship with eco-friendly suppliers and dealers to make GHRM efforts a success. Participant P7 who works in a renowned lifestyle retailer in Bangladesh firmly believed that without integrating GHRM practices with the whole supply chain operations of the organization, GHRM cannot be implemented in true sense. Participant P17 stated that without the support of external stakeholders, HR alone cannot effectively run sustainable HRM practices in a trustworthy manner and hence collaboration with them is vitally required. The following extracts address this perspective.

We need to completely collaborate with suppliers and artisans to integrate green practices into the entire supply chain and maybe one day name it, "Green Supply Chain". [P7]

"Furthermore, transparent communication and collaboration with external partners are essential for fostering trust and aligning interests in sustainable practices." [P17]

5. Discussion and Implications:

Taking a multiple industry perspective, this study explored the critical factors that impede the implementation of GHRM practices of organizations operating in Bangladesh. This exploration also identified some actions that are required to overcome the major impediments in this respect. This discussion section follows the sequence of the research questions of this exploratory study.

It is evident from this exploration that limited awareness and understanding of the employees regarding GHRM interventions and consequences cause a serious barrier to GHRM implementation (Rahman and Islam 2021; Noor et al.

2023). Findings suggest that when employees get reluctant about GHRM practices and deliberately resist the required changes in this regard, it hinders the adoption of environmentally responsible HRM initiatives (Hameed et al. 2023). It is however evident from the participants' expressions that the sociocultural background of the employees primarily causes them to show reluctance to accept any new change. It is found that excessive reliance on paper-based procedures made it challenging for most of the organizations in Bangladesh to shift from conventional HRM practice to eco-friendly digital GHRM practice (Ye et al. 2023). Lack of financial resource capabilities of the organization is found to be another critical impediment in this study. Organizations aspiring to integrate green aspects into their HRM practices require huge investment in sustainable hiring, developing, and maintaining practices, which is of course a major problem organizations of a developing country encounter (Ye et al. 2023). Findings imply that transitioning to sustainable HRM practices is an evolutionary process, encompassing significant cultural shift and adjustments (Hossari and Elfahli 2022). This subsequently requires ample investment of time that many organizations might not afford and hence time limitation can be attributed as a crucial impediment to GHRM implementation. Findings suggest that GHRM interventions failed to become effective in the workplace given that employees do not feel any motivation for their sustainable efforts. Employees usually feel demotivated when they do not notice any tangible rewards or benefits for their green behavior and actions (Hossari and Elfahli 2022; Mahdy et al. 2023). Findings also evidently indicate that incompatible regulatory policies of the external stakeholders act as a major impediment during the GHRM execution process. If the regulatory framework contradicts with the GHRM policies of the organization, implementing GHRM becomes undoubtedly a complex and challenging task for the HR team (Ye et al. 2023).

However, based on the participants' opinions and suggestions some actions can be proposed in this study that might help an organization to overcome the above discussed impediments and thereby implement GHRM policies and practices effectively. The first and foremost action required in this regard is to promote employee learning through organizing training, workshop, seminar, etc. Employee learning can be regarded as the cornerstone of effective GHRM execution, given that a well-informed and knowledgeable workforce can better embrace green HRM practices and contribute more competently. The role of training in developing employee awareness and understanding and thereby implementing GHRM practices is quite evident in the extant literature (Teixeira et al. 2012; Bombiak and Marciniuk-Kluska 2018; Islam et al. 2019). Since poor employee motivation is perceived to be a critical problem for GHRM practice, establishing an appropriate reward system for the workforce can be an effective solution. Acknowledging and rewarding employees for their contribution to green initiatives is instrumental for robust GHRM execution. Findings of this study imply that incorporating a well-organized reward system into the GHRM strategy of the organization is essential not only to support sustainability goals but also to enhance employee job satisfaction and engagement (Jabbour et al. 2008; Jackson et al. 2011; Islam et al. 2019). It is evident from the research findings that resistance to change severely impedes GHRM implementation which can be resolved by ensuring employee's active participation. Employee participation can be viewed as the green engine that creates a supportive ecosystem for GHRM practice, facilitating the organization to tame obstacles and thus lead sustainable HRM practices onward (Islam et al. 2019). Nurturing a paper-less office culture is assumed to be an effective action that an organization can undertake to rule out the deeply ingrained paper-based practice which is inconsistent with GHRM principles. Though establishing a paper-less culture may initially involve some investments, it will eventually lead to a more cost effective HRM practice (Alabaddi et al. 2020; Anjum et al. 2022). The financial constraints and time limitations can subsequently be mitigated. Moreover, findings of this study suggest that leveraging technology is essentially required for effective GHRM implementation, given that without the adoption of advanced technology it is impossible to create a paper-less organizational culture (Anjum et al. 2022). It can be argued that workplace sustainability cannot be achieved if electronic HRM is not integrated well with the GHRM initiatives of an organization (Phillips 2007). Finally, this exploration also found that aligning the GHRM policies and practices with the overall supply chain is crucial to minimize the complexities involved in GHRM execution

process. GHRM initiatives which are aligned with the whole supply chain of the business can better ensure that sustainability practices perfuse the whole ecosystem of the organization (Naseer et al. 2023). Though not well explored from the participants opinions, it can also be recommended that the regulatory bodies operating in Bangladesh like Bangladesh bank, Bangladesh securities and exchange commission, etc. should formulate environment friendly policies for different industries so that organizations can uninterruptedly execute sustainable HRM practices at the workplace, which will eventually benefit all the stakeholders of the broader society.

This exploratory research contributes to the knowledge by identifying the major impediments to GHRM implementation particularly in the context of multiple industries of Bangladesh which to the best of the author’s knowledge has not been rigorously explored earlier. One study was conducted in this respect which however considers only the RMG industry of Bangladesh (Islam et al. 2019). This study also contributes to the extant literature by proposing some valuable actions based on participants’ opinions that can be undertaken to seize the GHRM related complexities and barriers. The findings of this study have some practical implications as well. It can enable the HR managers of any type of organization to comprehend the potential difficulties and obstructions involved in GHRM execution and guide them to assume appropriate actions to fix the problems. The relevant stakeholders like employees, owners, suppliers, regulators will also be able to address the factors inhibiting GHRM practices and put efforts accordingly to make GHRM efforts a success. However, considering the specific socio-economic context of Bangladesh, and based on the impediments identified and actions suggested in this study, a framework for GHRM implementation can be offered here to guide organizations to take practical steps in a systematic manner.

Figure: GHRM Implementation Framework

6. Conclusions:

Based on the interviews with HR specialists of twenty-two different organizations operating in Bangladesh, this exploratory study identifies some major impediments of GHRM implementation such as limited employee awareness and understanding, resistance to change, deeply ingrained paper-based culture, financial restraints, excessive time requirements, employee demotivation, and incongruent regulatory policies. This paper also proposes some actions based on the opinions of the research participants that are needed for overcoming the identified barriers: promoting

learning, instituting appropriate reward systems, ensuring employee involvement and participation, breeding a paperless culture, leveraging technology, and aligning GHRM strategies with the supply chain operations. It is recommended that the relevant stakeholders such as managers, employees, owners, suppliers, customers, regulators, and all others should be concerned about the factors that can hinder GHRM execution at the workplace. This study is basically amongst the first, revealing a poorly explored phenomenon in multiple industry context and hence contributes to both the theory and practice. Researchers and practitioners can benefit from this study since the study not only explores the complexities involved in GHRM practice but rather advocates some solutions. However, the findings of this study cannot be generalized since it covers a small sample size and only one participant from each organization is selected for interview applying convenience sampling technique to explore the research topic. Multiple case study research in multiple industry context can be conducted in future to gain more context specific rich information and in-depth insights. A diverse sampling strategy needs to be employed in future to minimize the risk of bias and its impact on generalizability of findings. It would also be interesting to assess the severity of each impediment identified in this study by using a questionnaire survey method. Future studies could also investigate the long-term impacts of the proposed remedies on GHRM practices in Bangladesh.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: The author has read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Alabaddi, Z. A., Rahahleh, A. H., Muflih, M. A., Sana'a, N. A. N. and Salah, A. A. (2020) The role of electronic human resource management on the practices of green human resource management. *European Journal of Business and Management* 12(1), 55-72.
- [2] Anjum, N., Rahaman, M. S., Choudhury, M. I. and Rahman, M. M. (2022) An Insight into Green HRM Practices for Sustainable Workplace in the Banking Sector of Bangladesh: The Role of Electronic HRM. *Journal of Business Strategy Finance and Management* 04 (1), 66-80.
- [3] Benevene, P. and Buonomo, I. (2020) Green Human Resource Management: An Evidence-Based Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainability* 12, 5974, 1-25. doi:10.3390/su12155974
- [4] Bohdanowicz, P., (2006) Environmental awareness and initiatives in the Swedish and Polish hotel industries – survey results. *International Journal of Hospitality Management* 25 (4), 662-682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2005.06.006>.
- [5] Bombiak, E. and Marciniuk-Kluska, A. (2018) Green human resource management as a tool for the sustainable development of enterprises: Polish young company experience. *Sustainability* 10(6), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10061739>
- [6] Brockett, J. (2007) Prepare now for big rise in 'green' jobs, *People Management*, 9.
- [7] Chowdhury, S. H., Roy, S. K., Arafin, M. and Siddiquee, S. (2019) Green HR Practices and Its Impact on Employee Work Satisfaction - A Case Study on IBBL, Bangladesh. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)* 3 (3), 129-138.
- [8] Dumont, J., Shen, J., and Deng, X. (2016) Effects of green HRM practices on employee workplace green behavior: The role of psychological green climate and employee green values. *Human Resource Management* 56 (4), 613-627.
- [9] Ehnert, I. (2009) Sustainable human resource management. London: Springer.

- [10] Fayyazi, M., Shahbazmoradi, S., Afshar, Z., and Shahbazmoradi, M. (2015) Investigating the barriers of the green human resource management implementation in oil industry. *Management science letters* 5(1), 101-108.
- [11] Govindarajulu, N. and Daily, B. F. (2004) Motivating employees for environmental improvement. *Industrial management & data systems* 104 (4), 364-372.
- [12] Guerci, M. and Carollo, L. (2016) A paradox view on green human resource management: Insights from the Italian context. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management* 27(2), 212-238. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2015.1033641>
- [13] Hameed, R., Rehman, N., Tufail, S. and Kiziloglu, M. (2023) Green human resource management and environmental knowledge: A moderated mediation model to endorse green CSR. *Front. Environ. Sci.* 11:1136957. doi: 10.3389/fenvs.2023.1136957
- [14] Hossari, H. and Elfahli, K. (2023) Green Human Resource Management: An Exploratory Study from Moroccan ISO 14001 Certified Companies. *Business, Management and Economics*. Intech Open. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.105565>.
- [15] Islam, M. A., Hack-Polay, D., Haque, A., Rahman, M. and Hossain, M. S. (2021) Moderating role of psychological empowerment on the relationship between green HRM practices and millennial employee retention in the hotel industry of Bangladesh. *Business Strategy and Development*, 1-13.
- [16] Islam, M. A., Hunt, A., Jantan, A. H., Hashim, H. and Chong, C. W. (2019) Exploring challenges and solutions in applying green human resource management practices for the sustainable workplace in the ready-made garment industry in Bangladesh. *Business Strategy and Development*, 1-12.
- [17] Jabbour, C. J. C. (2011) How green are HRM practices, organizational culture, learning and teamwork? A Brazilian study. *Industrial and Commercial Training* 43 (2), 98-105. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00197851111108926>
- [18] Jabbour, C. J. C. (2013) Environmental training in organizations: From a literature review to a framework for future research. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 74, 144-155.
- [19] Jabbour, C. J. C., Jugend, D., De Sousa Jabbour, A. B. L., Gunasekaran, A. and Latan, H. (2015) Green product development and performance of Brazilian firms: measuring the role of human and technical aspects. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 87 (1), 442-451.
- [20] Jabbour, C. J. C., and Santos, F. (2008) The central role of human resource management in the search for sustainable organizations. *International Journal of Human Resource Management* 19 (12), 2133-2154. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585190802479389>
- [21] Jabbour, C. J. C., Santos, F. C. A. and Nagano, M. S. (2010) Contributions of HRM throughout the stages of environmental management: methodological triangulation applied to companies in Brazil. *International Journal of Human Resource Management* 21 (7), 1049-1089.
- [22] Jackson, S., Renwick, D., Jabbour, C. J. C. and Muller-Camen, M. (2011) State-of-the-Art and Future Directions for Green Human Resource Management. *German Journal of Research in Human Resource Management* 25 (3), 99-116. <https://doi.org/10.1177/239700221102500203>.
- [23] Jafri, S. (2012) Green HR practices: An empirical study of certain automobile organizations of India. *Human Resource Management* 42, 6193-6198.
- [24] Kamrunnahar, M., Mahamud, A., Akter, J., Hossain, M. U. and Rahaman, M. A. (2023) The employee awareness of green human resource management practices and environmental cooperation in Bangladesh. *North American Academic Research* 6 (1), 137-153.
- [25] Kapil, P. (2015) Green HRM- Engaging Human Resource in reducing carbon footprint and enhancing environment sustainability: A case study-based approach. *International Journal of Engineering Technology Science and Research* 2 (special), 5-14.

- [26] Longoni, A., Luzzini, D. and Guerci, M. (2018) Deploying environmental management across functions: the relationship between green human resource management and green supply chain management. *Journal of Business Ethics* 151 (4), 1081-1095.
- [27] Mahdy, F., Alqahtani, M. and Binzafrah, F. Imperatives, Benefits, and Initiatives of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM): A Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainability* 15, 4866. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15064866>
- [28] Mahmood, A., Sandhu, M. A., Kanwal, S., and Iqbal, J. (2016) The effect of green HRM practices on sustainability: Evidence from manufacturing companies in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Social Science* 36 (1), 177-188.
- [29] Mamun, M. A. A. (2019) An Analysis of Employee Awareness on Green Human Resource Management Practices: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Human Resource Management Research* 9 (1), 14-21. DOI: 10.5923/j.hrmr.20190901.03
- [30] Mathapati, C. M. (2013) Green HRM: A strategic facet. *Tactful Management Research Journal* 2(2), 1-6.
- [31] Matthews, B. and Ross, L. (2010) *Research Methods: A practical guide for the social sciences*. Pearson Education Limited
- [32] Mehta, K. and Chugan, P. K. (2015) Green HRM in pursuit of environmentally sustainable business. *Universal Journal of Industrial and Business Management* 3 (3), 74-81.
- [33] Naseer, S., Song, H., Adu-Gyamfi, G., Abbass, K. and Naseer, S. (2023) Impact of green supply chain management and green human resource management practices on the sustainable performance of manufacturing firms in Pakistan. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 30, 48021-48035. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-25409-7>.
- [34] Noor, B., Ahsan, M. M., Hasan, K. K. and Rahman, R. (2023) Factors Influencing the Awareness of Green Human Resource Management Practices in Bangladesh: An Application of Hierarchical Logistic Regression Model. *Journal of Human University Natural Sciences* 50 (5), 187-200.
- [35] Pham, N. T., Hoang, H. T. and Phan, Q. P. T. (2020) Green human resource management: a comprehensive review and future research agenda. *International Journal of Manpower* 41 (7), 845-878.
- [36] Phillips, L. (2007) Go green to gain the edge over rivals. *People Management* 23 (9), 1-9.
- [37] Prasad, R. S. (2013) Green HRM-partner in sustainable competitive growth. *Journal of Management Sciences and Technology* 1 (1), 15-18.
- [38] Rakin, S. R., Yousuf, M. B. and Rubel, M. R. B. (2020) Socially Responsible HRM and Environmental Performance of Banking Organization in Bangladesh: Mediating Effect of Green Innovation. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies* 10 (4), 268-286.
- [39] Ren, S., Tang, G. and Jackson, S. E. (2018) Green human resource management research in emergence: A review and future directions. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management* 35 (3), 769-803. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10490-017-9532-1>
- [40] Renwick, D. W. S., Redman, T. and Maguire, S. (2013) Green human resource management: a review and research agenda. *International Journal of Management Reviews* 15 (1), 1-14.
- [41] Rubel, M. R. B., Kee, D. M. H. and Rimi, N. N. (2021) The influence of green HRM practices on green service behaviors: the mediating effect of green knowledge sharing. *Employee Relations: The International Journal* 43 (5), 996-1015.
- [42] Rubel, M. R. B., Kee, D. M. H. and Rimi, N. N. (2021) Green human resource management and supervisor pro-environmental behavior: The role of green work climate perceptions. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127669>
- [43] Rupa, R. A., Alam, S., Sultana, A. and Alam, J. (2023) The Impact of Green HRM Practices on Environmental Performance in Bangladesh: The Mediating Role of Sustainability-Oriented Employee Behavior. *PMIS Review* 2 (1), 1-25.
- [44] Saeed, B. B., Afsar, B., Hafeez, S., Khan, I., Tahir, M. and Afridi, M. A. (2019) Promoting employee's proenvironmental behavior through green human resource management practices. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management* 26 (2), 424-438. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1694>

- [45] Saha, S., Sarker, R. and Ahmed, S. M. (2020) Impact of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices in Garment industry: Bangladesh Perspective. *International Journal of Management and Accounting* 2(2), 22-30.
- [46] Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2015) *Research Methods for Business Students*. 7th edition, Pearson Education, Harlow.
- [47] Smedley, T. (2007) A little more conservation. *People Management*, 32-35.
- [48] Taylor, B. M., Lawrence, G. A. (2012) Agripolitical Organizations in Environmental Governance: Representing Farmer Interests in Regional Partnerships. *Journal of Environmental Policy and Planning*.
- [49] Teixeira, A. D., Jabbour, C. J. C. and Jabbour, S. L. B. (2012) Relationship between green management and environmental training in companies located in Brazil: A theoretical framework and case studies. *International Journal of Production Economics* 139 (2), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2012.01.009>
- [50] Tomer, S. and Rana, G. (2020) Green Human Resource Management: A Conceptual Study. In *ICRMAT*, 147-150.
- [51] Ullah, M. A., Islam, M. R. and Sultana, R. (2020) Green Human Resource Management Practices for Attaining Environmental Sustainability: A Case Study of Selected Business Enterprises in Bangladesh. *The Comilla University Journal of Business Studies* 07, 05-26.
- [52] Vij, P., Suri, S. and Singh, S. (2013) Green HRM – Delivering High Performance HR Systems. *International Journal of Marketing and Human Resource Management (IJMHRM)* 4 (2), 19-25.
- [53] Ye, P., Liu, Z., Wang, X. (2023) Barriers to green human resources management (GHRM) implementation in developing countries: evidence from China. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 30, 99570-99583. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-28697-1>

Author

Dr. Qazi Moinuddin Mahmud AFHEA

Associate Professor

Department of Management

Faculty of Business Studies

University of Dhaka

Email: qmmahmud@du.ac.bd

